

DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL QUALITIES THROUGH THE SPORT OF BADMINTON.

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Abstract: The article examines the main aspects of the history of badminton, its impact on the human body, technical and tactical preparation, development of physical skills, and the relationship between badminton and psychology.

Key words: badminton, game, athlete, physical qualities, tools, methods.

Badminton is one of the most difficult sports, as it requires high physical fitness from the athlete. Thus, badminton is one of the three sports that require the most energy. Nevertheless, badminton training has a positive effect and allows the human body to be affected in many ways. Among such effects, it is possible to highlight the development of strength, speed, endurance, as well as the improvement of mobility in the joints, which helps to acquire large-scale motor skills and cultivate strong-willed qualities. Thanks to regular training, coordination skills, flexibility and dexterity are developed, and it also has a beneficial effect on the development of the nervous and cardiorespiratory systems. And intense movement around the field allows players to keep their bodies in great shape.

According to research, badminton not only helps to strengthen physical qualities, but also improves the emotional state of the player. The simplicity and convenience of badminton allows people of any age and gender to play this sport, because you can use the most basic court or land. And the ability to dose the load in each case allows badminton to be used as a rehabilitation tool in rest houses, in various groups of general physical fitness. Thus, the mass development of this sport helps to achieve physical fitness, improve health and ensure the creative longevity of not only this person, but the entire nation. [1,11,21,31,41,51,61,71,8]

Badminton has been known to people for many years. But there is still no confirmed information about its origin. According to the historical sources that have reached us, games similar to badminton existed two thousand years ago. It was played by adults and children in Ancient Greece, India, China, Japan and African countries. Thus, in Japan, the game is called "oibane". In France, such a game was called "jedepe, which means "game with apples". English medieval woodcuts depict peasants throwing sticks at each other. In 1650, Queen Christina of Sweden built the "feather ball" field, which still exists today, not far from the Royal Palace in Stockholm. Modern badminton is believed to have originated in India. It originates from the Indian game of roopa . According to historical sources, British officers who served in India became addicted to this game and formed the Folkestone Officers' Club in 1875 upon their arrival. Thus, the first president of the badminton association was Colonel Dolby, who took an active part in creating new rules of the game. [2,12,22,32,42,52,62,72,82,] These rules were based on the rules of the Indian game "roopa". Some of their game rules have survived to this day. Over time, new clubs began to appear in England. The game of shuttlecock also became popular near London, and its center was Badminton Place , which received its new name. Thanks to popularization, the new sport has increasingly covered

Europe, Asia and America. On July 5, 1934, the International Badminton Federation (IBF) was established and began to hold competitions. Badminton became an Olympic sport in 1992. In 2006, the IBF changed its name and is now known as the Badminton World Federation (BWF). The development of domestic badminton dates back to 1957. It was at that time that the World Festival of Youth and Students was held in Moscow. The first international meetings of our athletes took place at the festival. In the same year, the Cosmonaut Cup tournament was organized. The first cosmonaut of the Soviet Union Yu.A. In an interview after his historic flight, Gagarin said that he liked to play badminton because the game was fun for people. In 1974, the Soviet Union became a member of the International Badminton Federation. [3,13,23,33,43,53,63,73,83]

Badminton is a ball game with feathers. Two (singles) and four (doubles) players can participate in this game. The place for the game should be on a flat field that is closed from the wind. Players take opposite sides of the court and take turns hitting the racket and trying to pass it over the net to the opponent's side so that it touches the surface of the court. Players score three games up to 21 points (up to two wins in games). The side that wins the point adds it to their score. If the score is 20–20, the side with 2 consecutive points wins the game. At 29–29, the side with the 30th point wins the game. The winning side gets the right to start the match in the next set. [4,14,24,34,44,54,64,74,84]

Badminton is unique in that it can be played both indoors and outdoors. This versatile sport is suitable for both young children and adults. The secret of badminton's popularity is simple. This is a very simple game, it only needs rackets, which can be replaced with even the simplest devices if you wish.

Badminton:

- provides physical activity;
- does not require serious financial investments;
- suitable for different age groups; - serves for a long time;
- improves vision.
- develops the qualities of agility and flexibility

Taking into account the impact of the game on the human body and its use in recreational physical education, we can say that badminton has a number of advantages due to its effective effect on the metabolic processes occurring in the human body. It is possible to connect with such physical exercises, their performance is accompanied by the most accurate functioning of the main support systems. Playing badminton allows you to achieve the same activating effect on metabolic processes in the body, as well as other types of high-intensity muscle work. It is also effective in preventing a decrease in adaptive capacity. Experts have found that badminton training has a positive effect on all body systems, especially the cardiorespiratory system. In fact, the heart rate during the game can be 170 beats per minute or more.

Playing badminton is an effective tool for improving the general body, relieving stress, and developing various physical qualities, such as agility, speed, endurance, etc. It should also be noted that playing badminton affects the speed of thinking . It is not surprising that badminton is called "racquet chess", because during the game the badminton player has to calculate the "moves" very quickly - how the opponent will respond to his shot and how he will respond with different probabilities. The player must calculate several options for shots

at the same time. For this you need a high speed of thinking, which develops only during training and competition. During the game, participants must follow the flight path of the flywheel, which serves as a useful gymnastics for the eyes, as well as perform many bends, jumps and extensions. Badminton helps not only to strengthen the physical functional state, but also to improve the emotional state of the player. [5,15,25,35,45,55,65,75,85]

After long studies, experts came to the conclusion that badminton improves the blood circulation of the organs of vision, because the shuttlecock, moving closer to the eye or moving away from it, trains the oculomotor apparatus very well. During research, the Badminton Federation found that this sport helps with many vision problems, because during the game there are constant movements of the muscles responsible for focusing the vision. These muscles become stronger and many diseases do not develop, and the eyesight of those who regularly practice badminton improves significantly. All muscle groups are involved during badminton games, including the eye muscles and several other muscles. Watching the flywheel fly during the game replaces the exercises that ophthalmologists recommend as gymnastics for the eyes. There are also special computer programs that work on the same principle of tracking the approach and removal of an object with the eye. It turns out that this set of exercises is used involuntarily during badminton training and matches. And leading ophthalmologists confirmed these observations. So, the height of the standard field is 12 meters, the width of the field is 6 meters, the length is -13, an hour of training the eye, watching their various movements in the air, in the air they get the necessary load. Eye muscle training is available, thereby reducing accommodation spasm and improving vision. Distillation of blood to the heart, blood vessels, cerebral cortex, increases blood supply to all organs, and as a result, active training is obtained in a comfortable mode for the eyes. This is a scientifically proven fact. As for adults, the view here is not bad at all. In children, it is significantly improved by exercising the weakened eye muscles.

Badminton has another important quality - almost everyone can easily master it. Those who play badminton and take part actively move, get great physical load, great emotional energy. In this regard, the UNESCO special commission classified badminton as one of the sports that contribute to human health and well-being. Badminton combines lunges, jumps and arm movements with constant bending, active bending. Badminton also involves strong leg exercises. In one game, the athlete runs at a maximum speed of about six kilometers. Time shows that in just one game, a player has to swing the racket more than 500 times [4].

Psychological studies have shown that people who regularly do physical exercises experience less stress, feel comfortable, and daily worries do not cause a feeling of fatigue. As a rule, such people have increased efficiency. Rational, regular physical training can slow down aging to a certain extent. Scientists believe that the onset of aging, although not preventable, can be largely slowed down. There is a view that complaints about diseases are wrongly attributed to aging processes and diseases, which are probably caused by underdeveloped muscles and chronic underloading of the heart. Studies conducted by local scientists have shown that people who have been involved in health groups for twenty years are 10-15 years younger than their peers in terms of the condition of the motor area. According to German scientists, the functional state of the cardiovascular system and respiratory system remains at the level of 30 years old in people aged 50-60 who train according to a special program. And badminton can be included in this group of physical exercises. Vigorous movements around

the field help players keep their bodies in great shape and prevent excess weight. [7,17,27,37,47,57,67,87]

One of the main elements of training badminton players is technical training. Technical training means a set of movement skills required or actually acquired during training, as well as the level of their mastery. The main task of technical training is the formation of such skills for performing competitive actions that allow a badminton player to use his abilities as effectively as possible in competitions and ensure the continuous improvement of technical skills during many years of playing sports. The complexity of performing many technical elements in badminton is explained by the fact that the athlete has to solve several problems at the same time: to monitor the correctness of the movement scheme, to keep the flying racket in sight and, finally, to approach it. timely and accurate. Jumping in badminton stimulates the strengthening of bones and ligaments. But at the same time, the jumping technique of movement in badminton does not have a negative effect on the spine, because. From the initial training, players learn to move with soft jumps, almost without landing on the heel (when landing on the ankle, the impact load on the spine appears), thereby minimizing the load on the spine.

All this requires the comprehensive development of physical qualities, so the teacher must first of all establish motor skills and only then proceed directly to training.

Thus, before direct training in badminton, there is a general educational stage related to the development of physical qualities and skills. The modern game of badminton requires the ability of the athlete to perform technical elements quickly and for a sufficiently long time, often at the limits of physical capabilities. In the conditions of the competition, the heavy work regime is not typical for every athlete, so the development of the badminton player's physical qualities and increasing his physical fitness become the main content of sports training. Physical training of a badminton player is aimed at comprehensive development of the body, strengthening of health and improvement of movement characteristics. To solve these problems, various general developmental exercises such as bending, twisting, swinging, and jumping are widely used; weight training; exercises in simulators, etc. There are also special physical training tools and methods, which are suitable for developing and improving motor qualities and skills, mainly for increasing speed, speed endurance, joint mobility and muscle elasticity, agility and coordination of movements. intended. [8,18,28,38,48,58,68,78,88].

Thus, the main goal is to develop physical qualities such as speed-strength qualities, endurance, agility and flexibility. Let's take a closer look at each quality.

One of the most important qualities in badminton is speed - the ability to perform movements in the shortest time for a given condition. According to experts, speed abilities are more innate and less likely to change during training. It was found that increasing the speed can be achieved not only by using special methods and tools aimed at developing the ability to self-accelerate, but also indirectly by developing strength qualities, speed-power abilities, and improving abilities. movement technique. Traditionally, all exercises used to develop speed-power qualities in badminton are divided into three groups:

1. Exercises to overcome your own body weight: fast running, movement with a change of direction, various jumps, as well as high-speed bending, body twisting exercises.
2. Exercises performed with additional weights (belt, cuff, weighted projectile).

3. Exercises related to overcoming the resistance of the external environment (water, snow, wind, soft ground, running uphill, etc.).

The speed-strength training system is aimed at solving the main task - the speed of movements and the development of the strength of a certain muscle group.

Endurance means the ability to perform a certain task for a long time. An athlete with high functionality, excellent metabolic processes and reasonable technique can withstand a difficult game mode associated with high energy consumption, intensive almost limited work of the cardiovascular system.

To develop endurance, it is recommended to use running, swimming, rowing, sports and outdoor games, jumping rope and other exercises. In addition, in badminton, as a means of complex impact on the body, the method of circular exercises is used, which consists in continuously performing all the exercises included in the "circle". To develop endurance in the gym, you can use simulation and game exercises, exercises with a flywheel performed in interval mode. The importance of these exercises is that, using them, the athlete simultaneously improves physical qualities, the technique of moving around the field, and the technique of various shots. To achieve a high level of endurance, an athlete must not only have a high level of individual characteristics and abilities, but also be able to show them in harmony. [9,19,29,39,49,59,69,79,87]

Agility can be defined, firstly, as the ability to quickly learn new movements, and secondly, as the ability to quickly reorganize movement activities in accordance with the requirements of a suddenly changing environment. Agility is based on mobility of motor skills, as well as highly developed muscle sensation and plasticity of neural processes. The better a badminton player's perception and perception of his movements, the faster he learns new exercises. Technical training is inextricably linked with the development of dexterity. In the training system of a badminton player, relaxation exercises, as well as throwing, juggling, and flexibility exercises are widely used, indicating the flight time and distance. The best means of developing agility are open games, trampoline, acrobatic exercises, activities that include elements of innovation and improvisation.

Flexibility is the ability to perform large-amplitude movements. Insufficient mobility in joints restricts movement, restricts them. Without this quality, proper technique cannot be mastered. Technical elements in badminton require great mobility of the spine, shoulder, elbow, and wrist joints. Flexibility is a quality that is easily formed. Stretching exercises performed with maximum amplitude should be used as a means of training flexibility. Flexibility exercises can be dynamic or static. The combination of spring movements with the fixation of the subsequent position has the greatest effect on the development of flexibility. Flexibility exercises should precede an active warm-up. Such exercises are most effective if performed several times a day.

In addition to the development of physical qualities, attention should also be paid to tactical training. Sports tactics is the art of fighting, the ability to rationally use the strengths of one's training and the weaknesses of the opponent's training. [10,20,30,40,50,60,70,80,]

In the process of technical and tactical preparation, it is necessary to strive to create conditions that are close to real game situations. In addition, tactical training requires knowledge of the rules of the game, general practical information about the principles and rational forms of tactics, as well as a battle formed taking into account preliminary general

information about actual and combat actions. includes specific tactical options for transfer. potential competitors [5].

Thus, the level of tactical thinking, technical skills and physical fitness form a complex that is necessary to solve different situations in badminton.

If we look at badminton from the point of view of psychology, firstly, badminton is almost the only game in size. Almost all other game sports (hockey, tennis, football) are plane games, where the projectile moves in a plane (basketball, volleyball have some similarity in size, but these are team sports). The shuttlecock flies with a large amplitude up and down, as well as in width and depth, approaching and retreating. Accordingly, having the size of a badminton, as well as a small, fast-moving racket, we will have an excellent tool for the neuropsychological development of spatial thinking, the connection of the coordinates of our body with space, and the development of physiological and psychological vision. . If we draw an analogy between badminton and psychology, then one of the most important concepts is the concept of "goal". If we look carefully at the development of life, we will see that our whole life consists of goals - small and big, easily achieved and completely unattainable (in our opinion, this point of view may be wrong). So, in badminton - there are goals. We can say that the small goal is to hit the shuttlecock, and the big one is to win the championship or the Olympics. But for a small child, even a small goal like hitting the crossbar becomes a big goal. And this is only the first goal. The next goal is to hit over the net. By the way, what is a network ? This is a barrier. An obstacle to achieving the goal. After all, it is the same in life. If there is a goal in life, there will be obstacles to achieve it. And this obstacle must be overcome. This is for the young badminton player. In order for the shuttle to fly to the enemy's side, it is necessary to overcome an obstacle - a net - to reach a new goal. This will also be difficult at first and will require several strenuous exercises. But this goal will be achieved and there will be joy again! The child already understands that achieving goals, firstly, is real, and secondly, he knows that it brings a lot of positive emotions. He strives to set new goals for himself, because he is not afraid of them. So, in small steps, most importantly, in a playful way, a strong-willed person is brought up, who will step into a big life and achieve great success, regardless of whether this little athlete will grow up to become a champion. or not. For adult players of all levels of the game, there are also goals in each game, and each game becomes a goal. By the way, it has been noted that those who played badminton in childhood will connect their future life with this sport in one way or another. Even those who left it for some reason return to badminton.

The second concept that connects badminton with psychology is the concept of "self-expression". If you are thinking about this word, then self-expression is our life. Man manifests himself and lives by it. If a person does not manifest himself in any way, then he does not exist. If a person does not express himself adequately, he feels that something is wrong in his life. Everyone here is different from a little dissatisfaction with their life to a deep depression. Playing badminton allows a person to express themselves due to their ability and level of play. For each person, self-expression is manifested in different ways in life: at work, in the family, in creativity. If a person cannot express himself in these areas of life, he looks for areas that allow him to express himself with his body. After all, a person is, first of all, a body. The easiest and most convenient place for the body to work is sports. But what kind of sport is there for someone who hasn't played sports since childhood? It is difficult for such a person to come to gymnastics, for example, team sports, where you need

to find a team of at least 2 players of your level, and it is not easy. And in badminton, it is enough to find one person at your level of play, start playing, start showing yourself in the game and enjoy the joy of showing yourself. Thus, playing badminton, a person gets an interesting and exciting exercise, gets a coping mechanism, learns and improves control of his body. It increases self-confidence, self-confidence, which affects all areas of his life. A person is psychologically resistant to all the difficulties that he faces in life. Solving any psychological problem requires solving problems related to self-confidence, overcoming oneself and working on oneself. Like any sports competition, badminton is about realizing your aggression, overcoming uncertainty, getting rid of stress, etc.

Gradually, we came to the third concept that connects badminton and psychology - the concept of "self-development". There are no boundaries in badminton. After learning elementary kicks, the technique of these kicks will be further refined. And since badminton has a lot of shots and even more combinations of shots, you can work endlessly in this direction. Even sports masters are working on improving their shots. And if we talk about amateurs, then their opportunities for self-improvement are truly unlimited, you need to work on walking and acting on the field. Here, as in achieving a goal, a person who sees progress in mastering the game gains confidence. Because there is such a moment in badminton - if a person plays badminton regularly, his game will improve by itself. The secret is that a person seeks to improve the game of his own free will, and no one and nothing forces him. Are there many moments in life when you want to work and work more than you need to? Thus, it can be said that playing improves the human body and soul, improves the general psychological state. A person believes in life, radiates joy and positive energy. It is very difficult to find boring and sad people among badminton players. As a hypothesis, it is possible to highlight another thing that affects the psychological health of those who play badminton. Remember, in childhood, a small person builds a house for himself from his own tools, thereby limiting the world around him. Why is the child doing this? To limit oneself from the outside world and create one's own world. This self-world, limited by frameworks, embraces security and predictability. It is a world where the child decides whether it is light or dark. It is a world where the child feels like the boss, where he decides who to let in and who not to. When a person plays on the field, he also finds himself to a certain extent in such a world, which is limited by frames (field lines). And this world is just as safe and predictable as the larger world that surrounds us in everyday life. A person who comes to the club after work, playing badminton, throws away all the problems and fatigue from the day's work. As it turns out, it falls into some kind of "rest zone". Also, remember that childhood is a time of play, a time free from worries. Therefore, when a person immerses himself in the game, he gets rid of worries. This is especially evident in those who played badminton as children. Entering the game activates the "time machine" effect, a person goes back to his childhood, where he lived easily and carelessly. Psychologists say that many relaxation and mind-altering methods (for example, yoga, breathing techniques, etc.) are aimed at returning a person to the states he was in when he was a child. This is done so that a person can find new sources for life in this state and change his mind. So, we can say that playing badminton, a person gets an explosion of emotions from the game, and at the same time relaxes, relaxes, distracts from everyday worries. And since badminton is available to everyone, changing one's psychological state is also available to everyone. In fact, our life is often monotonous - "home-work-home-work", and for psychological health it is very necessary to switch to such

a different rhythm. I would also like to emphasize that badminton helps to overcome loneliness. Recently, the popularity of badminton has been growing rapidly, primarily due to its availability. Many badminton clubs are being established in many cities. There are communities of people who are passionate about this game, and a person who visits the badminton courts can feel his importance to others, a sense of unity with a community of badminton enthusiasts belonging to an important group. He can feel that they are waiting for him there. In addition, there is no need to gather large companies, as in football, hockey, volleyball, just take a racket and come to the nearest club, there is always someone to play with [7].

Badminton is one of the oldest games. Sources with a long history speak of its existence. Thus, several thousand years before our era, people noticed the positive effect of this game on health and the development of the body in general. And indeed it is. Badminton rightfully occupies one of the leading places among games with healing and training effects. This sport has a beneficial effect on the metabolic processes occurring in the human body. Compared to other sports, badminton has a number of advantages. Thus, contact with the opponent and related injuries are excluded, the load can be dosed, and badminton does not require a large number of people, special large-sized sites. It is open to people of all ages and easy to learn for beginners.

Conclusion: Playing badminton, which has a complex effect on the human body, helps to develop strength, endurance, speed, as well as flexibility and agility. In the course of regular training, coordination skills are developed, joint mobility is improved, it has a beneficial effect on the development of the nervous and cardio-respiratory systems, and strong willed qualities are cultivated. Tactical thinking and technical skills, in addition to physical qualities, help athletes to make quick decisions in various game situations, assess the opponent's situation and take active actions aimed at achieving high sports results.

Badminton is very popular among the population. To play badminton, you need a very simple inventory - rackets, shuttlecock, net. Finding a place to play is easy. Thus, the game of badminton has high health and training potential. Due to its training potential, playing badminton appears to be one of the most effective, affordable and attractive forms of fitness for people of almost any age and fitness level.

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